

Genetic Diversity Analysis of Rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum* L.) Using Dna Barcodes and ISSR Markers

Author's Details:

Do Tan Khang¹, Nguyen Pham Hong Dao¹, Chau Ngoc Tuyen¹, Nguyen Pham Anh Thi¹, Nguyen Van Ay³, Tran Gia Huy¹, Tran Nhan Dung¹ and Tran Thanh Men²

¹Biotechnology Research and Development Institute, Can Tho University, Vietnam

²College of Natural Sciences, Can Tho University, Vietnam

³College of Agriculture, Can Tho University, Vietnam

Corresponding author: dtkhang@ctu.edu.vn

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Abstract

Rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum* L.) brings enormous economic value for Vietnam. It is necessary to support the basic research to analyze genetic diversity among rambutan cultivars for identification and conservation. The objectives of this study were to analyze the genetic diversity by DNA barcodes and evaluate polymorphism by ISSR markers on eight rambutan cultivars. Fourteen specimens of eight rambutan cultivars collected to detect the differences in their genotype on the *matK* and ITS region, combined with ISSR technique. *matK* gene was sequenced on 12 specimens of rambutan and clustered into three groups on the phylogenetic tree. Besides, nine SNP locations have also been recorded in *matK* gene and five of them could be used to identify three cultivars including yellow-flesh rambutan, Java rambutan, and the hybrid rambutan Tien Cuong. Results of the polymorphism combining ISSR 10 and ISSR 23 primers gave an average of 11 polymorphic bands per primer. In which, six polymorphic bands were recorded to identify the original rambutan, yellow-flesh rambutan and the hybrid rambutan Tien Cuong. As a conclusion, these diverse characters could be potentially applied in rambutan cultivars identification as well as building a DNA database for Vietnamese rambutan.

Keywords: DNA barcode, ISSR, ITS, *matK*, rambutan

INTRODUCTION

Rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum* L.) is a tropical fruit originated from Malaysia and popularly grown in Asian, African and South American countries (Sukmandari *et al.*, 2017). In Vietnam, there are four rambutan varieties that widely grown and exported to US, Canada, New Zealand, Dubai, Europe and Asia. They are Nhan rambutan, Java rambutan, Thai rambutan and the original Vietnamese rambutan.

However, due to the breed degradation, crossbreeding and mix-multiple varieties for the profit increase demands, the valuable features of each variety would be lost. These problems may lead to the confusion and negative impression for the domestic and foreign customers. To solve that issue, the question is how to identify accurately and objectively among rambutan varieties, instead of observing the morphology only. One of the solutions may come from the molecular techniques such as DNA barcodes or ISSR markers analysis, which evaluates deep into the differences in genotype of each variety. DNA barcode for identification of rambutan varieties not only helps to improve the limitations of the manual methods, which ask for time-consuming and highly specialized. The results of these techniques could be applied to other domains such as country security and defense, import and export, biodiversity and conservation.

Therefore, study was conducted on the *matK* gene in chloroplasts and the ITS sequence region in the nucleus, combined with ISSR markers to detect the differences in genotypes between rambutan varieties. From that result, the study contributed to the identification and conservation varieties as well as brand protection for Vietnamese rambutan go further in the future.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials

Fourteen specimens belong to eight rambutan cultivars selected from four districts of Vietnam were used in this study. The specimen numbers and district of origin were listed in Table 1.

Methods

DNA extraction

DNA was extracted from fresh and young leaves by CTAB protocol (Doyle, 1991) with some modifications. The modifications include the addition of double the amount of PVP40 and 2-mercaptoethanol in the EB solution and increasing the amount of ethanol. DNA quality was determined by 1% agarose gel electrophoresis.

matK and ITS – PCR analysis

One chloroplast DNA regions and one nuclear ribosomal DNA region were amplified. Primers for the chloroplast regions are *matK*-4600/*trnK*-2R described in Edwards and Gadek (2001). Primers for the ITS region are ITS1/ITS4 described in White et al (1990).

Amplification of selected regions were achieved in a 30 μ L reaction for each primer, contained: 12 μ L Master Mix (including KCl, MgCl₂, dNTPs, Taq polymerase from Meridian Bioscience Inc), 0.25 μ L of 20 pmol/ μ L primer, 2 μ L DNA template and 15.5 μ L BiH₂O. PCR were performed in Biorad C1000 Thermal Cycler system.

Table 1: Studied rambutan specimens and their geographical origins

Specimens name	Location	Code
1	Can Tho	NC
2 Nhan rambutan	Ben Tre	NB
3	Vinh Long	NV
4	Can Tho	TC
5 Thai rambutan	Ben Tre	TB
6	Vinh Long	TV
7	Can Tho	JC
8 Java rambutan	Ben Tre	JB
9	Vinh Long	JV
10 Indo rambutan	Vinh Long	I
11 Original rambutan	Can Tho	O
12 Yellow peel rambutan	Can Tho	V
13 Yellow flesh rambutan	Dak Lak	R
14 Tien Cuong rambutan hybrid	Ben Tre	L

For the *matK*-4600/*trnK*-2R primer pair, PCR amplification followed the procedure in Buerki *et al.* (2009) with some optimization. The initial denaturation at 95°C for 2 min followed by 20 cycles: denaturation at 95°C for 45 sec, annealing at 59°C for 1 min, extension at 72°C for 1 min, with final extension at 72°C for 10 min. For the ITS1/ITS4 primer pair, PCR amplification was performed in a thermal cycler following several steps which are an initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 min followed by 25 cycles: denaturation at 95°C for 30 sec, annealing at 56°C for 30 sec, extension at 72°C for 1 min 10 sec, with final extension at 72°C for 10 min. PCR amplification products along with 100 bp and 1 kb DNA ladder were separated by electrophoresis in 2% agarose gel (1x TAE) (stained with Safeview) for 50 min at 50 volts. The gel was visualized on UV and photographed using Molecular Imager ChemiDoc XRS System from BioRad.

matK and ITS data analysis

The PCR products amplified from *matK* and ITS primers were sent to NEXTGENE Inc. for DNA sequencing. These sequences were then uploaded into the BLAST tool in NCBI for comparison with the sequence of rambutan cultivars published on Genbank. All of the rambutan sequences initially aligned and

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thereafter manually adjusted with the Bioedit software. The variety of nucleotide between sequences (SNP) was the standard to draw the phylogenetic tree on MegaX software to analysis genetic diversity between rambutan cultivars.

ISSR data analysis

Using DNA specimens extracted in section 2.1 to continue conducting polymorphism analysis with ISSR marker. Based on the research Madihah *et al.* (2018) on Indonesia rambutan cultivars, there are two ISSR primers were selected to show the clearest and highest polymorphic band in rambutan: **ISSR10**: (GA)₆C; **ISSR23**: (GACA)₃CC.

According to the procedure in Madihah *et al.* (2018), DNA amplification was performed using a total of 25 μ L reaction mixture containing 2 μ L of template DNA, 0.25 μ L of primers (10 pmol/ μ l), 12.5 μ L Master Mix (including KCl, MgCl₂, dNTPs, Taq polymerase from Meridian Bioscience Inc) and 9.5 μ L BiH₂O. PCR amplification followed Madihah *et al.* (2018) with some optimization: the initial denaturation at 94°C for 3 minutes; 30 cycles of denaturing at 94°C for 1 minute, annealing at 45 - 47°C for 50 seconds, elongation at 72°C for 2 minutes; and a final elongation at 72°C for 10 minutes. PCR amplification products along with 100 bp to 3 kb DNA ladder were separated by electrophoresis in 3% agarose gel (1 x TAE) (stained with Safeview) for 1 hour and 40 minutes at 25 volts. The gel was visualized on UV and photographed using Molecular Imager ChemiDoc XRS System from BioRad.

DNA band resulted from ISSR primer at the same location was scored as 1 and 0 coded for the presence and absence band respectively. The genetic relationship among rambutan cultivars was analyzed using UPGMA. Data analysis was performed using NTSYSpc software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Genetic diversity in gene *matK*

After optimization process, the PCR product electrophoresis spectrum on 2% agarose gel gave bright and clear bands without sub-band (Figure 1). The bands size were above 1000 bp, approximately 1500 bp. That result are suitable for the amplified products with the *matK*-4600/*trnK*-2R primer published by Edwards and Gadek (2001). These PCR products are sent for sequencing.

Figure 1. Gel electrophoresis of PCR products with *matK* primer

MI: marker 1kb, **NC:** nhan Can Tho, **NB:** nhan Ben Tre, **NV:** nhan Vinh Long, **TC:** Thai Can Tho, **TB:** Thai Ben Tre, **TV:** Thai Vĩnh Long, **JC:** Java Can Tha, **JB:** Java Ben Tre, **JV:** Java Vinh Long, **O:** ta rambutan, **R:** yellow-flesh rambutan, **V:** yellow-shell rambutan, **I:** Indo rambutan, **L:** hybrid rambutan Tien Cuong

A total of 12 sequences of 7 rambutan cultivars were successfully sequenced. With sizes the sequences range from 757 to 1169 bp. According to the research of Kong *et al.* (2014) in rambutan, the amplified *matK* gene region has size of 801 bp, which is equivalent to the average size of the amplified sequences in this study.

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BLAST result: there are three sequences that have the highest similarity with most Vietnamese rambutan cultivars, which are the species with code MT936934.1 (China's Baoyan rambutan variety), code AY724316.1 (*Nephelium mutabile* species) and code number AF314801.1 (also rambutan species).

Code MT936934.1 is the sequence of Baoyan rambutan variety of China published by Dong *et al.* (2020). This study has sequenced the whole chloroplast genome, including the *matK-trnK* region of rambutan. The highest level of similarity with this variety in the *matK* region is the yellow-flesh rambutan in Dak Lak with 99% query and 98.82% identity.

Code AY724316.1 is the sequence of *Nephelium mutabile* species in a report by Harrington *et al.* (2005). *Nephelium mutabile* or commonly known as Pulasan or Nephelium ramboutan-ake is a specialty fruit that has grown wild since ancient times in Malaysia. The morphology quite similar to rambutan but less hair density and much shorter, but stiffer. The taste is sweeter than rambutan, which is more succulent and especially the seeds are edible and have an almond flavor (Morton, 1987). The highest level of similarity with this species in the *matK* gene is Thai rambutan cultivar with 98% query and 98.73% identity. According to Harrington *et al.* (2005), Pulasan and rambutan exhibited a very close taxonomy because they are on the same branch in phylogenetic tree based on their *matK* genome data.

Code AF314801.1 is also a sequence of rambutan species published by Edwards and Gadek (2001). The highest degree of similarity with this species in the *matK* area is the yellow-shell rambutan in Phong Dien, Can Tho with 98% query and 99.03% identity and yellow-flesh rambutan with 99% query and 98.11% identify. From the above results, these three sequences were downloaded from NCBI and together with 12 sequences of this study, genetic sequencing analysis conducted using Bioedit software.

Analyzing the diversity in sequences

Nine reliable SNP locations were recorded. Among them, there are five SNPs present in only one variety, showing the specificity for that variety. Therefore, the *matK-4600/trnK-2R* primer pair amplifies the *matK* gene could be used as DNA barcode to identify three cultivars: yellow-flesh rambutan, Java rambutan and the hybrid rambutan Tien Cuong. In addition, these SNP markers are also the standard to build the phylogenetic tree.

Analyzing phylogenetic tree

Phylogenetic tree formation between 15 sequences including 12 specimens of rambutan in the subject and 3 sequences of high similarity on NCBI. Phylogenetic trees were drawn using MegaX software with repeatable 1000 bootstrap index. The branches of phylogenetic trees show that the specimens in the experiment can be clustered into 3 main branches (Figure 2).

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Figure 2. Phylogenetic tree of 15 species/varieties in *Nephelium* genus by their *matK* gene

In detail, on the *matK* gene, there is almost no difference in genetically between the nhan rambutan and Thai rambutan, with the genetic distance is from 0.000 to 0.001. In the same branch 1 there are also have the hybrid rambutan Tien Cuong and the yellow-flesh rambutan with the genetic distance of 0.005 and 0.002 in comparison with nhan rambutan and Thai rambutan, with bootstrap index of 64% and 59% respectively.

The second branch: With genetic distance ranging from 0.000 to 0.003 and bootstrap index from 25% to 92%, there is almost no difference in genetics between the Java rambutan and the yellow-shell rambutan on the *matK* gene.

The third branch, beside the original rambutan in this study, also has the appearance of BLAST sequences found on NCBI. With genetic distance between 0.000 and 0.001 and bootstrap index between 72% and 95%.

Evaluation of ISSR primers

A total of 46 bands were amplified on a set of 8 cultivars - 14 rambutan specimens by 2 ISSR primers. The number of polymorphic bands in ISSR 23 primer is two more than ISSR 10. The sizes of polymorphic bands range from 200 to 1500 bp (Figure 3). Each ISSR primer gave an average of 11 polymorphic bands, accounting for 47.8% of the total amplified bands per specimen.

This result is similar to the study of Napitu *et al.* (2016) on five rambutan cultivars, collected in five provinces of Indonesia. Also with two ISSR primers used, the ratio of polymorphic bands observed ranged from 25 - 87.5% of the total band. In which, 3 out of 5 provinces have the rate of polymorphic band close to the result of this study is 44 - 56% of the total bands. And the research by Qiu *et al.* (2007) on *Dipteronia dyerana* belonging to *Sapindaceae* family in Yunnan province, China also showed 70.8% polymorphic bands in total and average 15.4 bands generated from each primer of 10 ISSR primers.

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Figure 3. Gel electrophoresis with (A) ISSR 10 and (B) ISSR 23

M2: marker 3kb, **NC:** nhan Can Tho, **NB:** nhan Ben Tre, **NV:** nhan Vinh Long, **TC:** Thai Can Tho, **TB:** Thai Ben Tre, **TV:** Thai Vinh Long, **JC:** Java Can Tha, **JB:** Java Ben Tre, **JV:** Java Vinh Long, **O:** ta rambutan, **R:** yellow-flesh rambutan, **V:** yellow-shell rambutan, **I:** Indo rambutan, **L:** hybrid rambutan Tien Cuong, **MI:** marker 1kb

According to Madihah *et al.* (2018), the six selected ISSR molecular markers amplified 87% of the total band as polymorphic bands of 30 Indonesian rambutan specimens. The average number of polymorphic bands per primer was also 13 to 21 bands. However, in the study of Degani *et al.* (2003) over 66 cultivars of lychee, from the same *Sapindaceae* family with rambutan, showed that 64% of polymorphic bands were recognized by 32 ISSR primers, with an average of 3.7 to 5.5 polymorphic bands per primer, much less than the 11 bands obtained from Vietnamese rambutan cultivars.

Based on these documents, the differences may come from the variety in the ISSR primer length and sequence used in each study. Specifically, in the study Degani *et al.* (2003), 32 ISSR primers were used, all of which have larger lengths and more complex sequences. Of which 27 per 32 primers consist of two repeat nu. and one to three anchor positions, total sizes up to 17 - 19 nu.. The other primers in that study, although have no anchor position, but the number of repeat nu. content three to five nu., forming poly-nucleotide primer with size from 15 to 18 nu.. From there, number of polymorphic bands from Degani *et al.* (2003) were also few and ranged from one to five bands per primer. In this study, two ISSR 10 and 23 primers are used, both of them have 14 nu. with a simple sequence structure, so it is easier to pair to more locations on rambutan genotype, thereby obtaining more polymorphic bands. However, the bands are not as clear as the results of Degani *et al.* (2003). Therefore, the primer designing is important to give reliable polymorphic results, suitable for different samples.

Clustering analysis

The polymorphic product based on this ISSR primer clustered eight cultivars - 14 rambutan specimens into four main groups, at the similarity coefficients of 84.8% (Figure 4). At the similarity level of 84.8%, there are two rambutan cultivars belonging to group 1, group 2 has 4 cultivars, while group 3 has only 1 variety of yellow-flesh rambutan and group 4 includes only Tien Cuong hybrid rambutan.

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Figure 4. Dendrogram of 14 rambutan varieties by ISSR markers

Besides, Tien Cuong hybrid rambutan could be identified with other cultivars based on the appearance of the three polymorphic bands with ISSR 10 and ISSR 23 primers. Similarly, the original rambutan could be identified with other rambutan cultivars by one polymorphic band at position 1100 bp of ISSR 23. And the yellow-flesh rambutan specimen appears a polymorphic band only in the 850 bp, while the other cultivars did not. The results of these polymorphic band positions may be the foundation for applying the ISSR 10 and ISSR 23 molecular markers to the identification of the hybrid Tien Cuong rambutan, yellow-flesh rambutan and the original rambutan of Vietnam.

CONCLUSIONS

matK gene of 12 specimens belonging to seven rambutan cultivars was successfully amplified. The obtained sequences have high similarity with those of *Nephelium lappaceum* and *Nephelium mutabile* on NCBI. Five out of nine specific SNP locations could be used to identify three cultivars of rambutan: the original rambutan, Java rambutan, and the hybrid rambutan Tien Cuong. Seven cultivars of rambutan above are clustered into three branches on the phylogenetic tree. Recorded some changes in the PCR thermal cycle to optimize the *matK* gene amplification and ITS region in rambutan specimens.

The results of polymorphism combining two ISSR 10 and ISSR 23 primers gave an average of 11 polymorphic bands per primer, accounting for 47.8% of the total amplified bands per specimen. In which, six polymorphic band positions were recorded in both primers which have the meaning of identifying the original rambutan, Tien Cuong hybrid rambutan and yellow-shell rambutan.

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